

University of
Nottingham
UK | CHINA | MALAYSIA

TURNEYES 892951

RESEARCHER ANNEMARIE WALTER
OUTGOING SUPERVISOR DAVID REDLAWSK
INCOMING SUPERVISOR CEES VAN DER EIJK

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Forgiveness: Born Again Christians and Severe Moral Transgressions by Politicians

Annemarie Walter & David Redlawsk

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Forgiveness: Born Again Christians and Severe Moral Transgressions by Politicians

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- How willing are American voters to forgive politicians involved in moral transgressions?
- Does partisanship and /or religion condition voters' willingness to forgive politicians' immoral behavior?

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Hypotheses

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- **Ingroup Forgiveness Hypothesis:** Respondents are more willing to forgive in-party transgressors than out-party transgressors
- **Partisan Strength Hypothesis:** The in-party bias in forgiveness is moderated by the strength of respondents' partisan identity.
- **Religion Hypothesis:** Religious respondents are more likely to forgive politicians for moral transgressions than non-religious respondents
- **Religiousness Hypothesis:** The more religious respondents are the more likely they are willing to forgive morally transgressive politicians
- **Born Again Christian Hypothesis:** Respondents who are born again Christians more likely to forgive politicians for moral transgressions than non-born again Christians

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Experimental Design

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- A vignette study using a between-subjects experiment in a 6 x 3 design embedded in a survey questionnaire administered to approximately 3000 U.S. voters
- We manipulated the moral principle violated (Care, Fairness, Loyalty, Authority and Sanctity) and added a social norm violation as a baseline
- We manipulated the partisanship of the politician (Republican, Democrat, no partisanship) in the vignette
- Each respondent was randomly assigned a short vignette describing a fictional, but realistic sounding, scenario
- Data were collected between 2 October 2020 and 3 November 2020 by Dynata
- Willingness to Forgive (0=No; 1=Yes)- The politician should be forgiven for his/her behavior

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Stimulus Material

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Moral Principle	Vignette	Wrong (Mean) Experiment
Care	You see a (Democrat/Republican/-) politician make fun of a constituent with mental health problems	4.07
Fairness	You see a (Democrat/Republican/-) politician making sure that those who voted for him get first access to jobs	3.92
Loyalty	You see a (Democrat/Republican/-) politician town say the neighbouring town is better	3.04
Authority	You see a (Democrat/Republican/-) politician violating safety regulations ordered by the Chief of Police/Chief Constable at a disaster	3.80
Sanctity	You see a (Democrat/Republican/-) politician was found having sex with a teenager	4.61
None	You see a (Democrat/Republican/-) politician carrying briefing papers to the capitol/Houses of Parliament in a plastic grocery bag	2.47

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The Effect of a Moral Transgression on Voters' Willingness to Forgive

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The Effect of Partisanship on Voters' Willingness to Forgive

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The Effect of Strength of Partisanship on Voters' In Party Bias in Willingness to Forgive

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The Effect of Religion on Voters' Willingness to Forgive

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The Effect of Religiousness on Voters' Willingness to Forgive

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Conclusions

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- Voters are more likely to forgive in party politicians for moral transgressions than out party politicians
- The in party bias in forgiveness is stronger for strong partisans than weak and leaning partisans.
- The more religious voters are the more likely they are forgive politicians for their moral transgressions
- Born again Christians are more likely to forgive politicians for moral transgressions other voters, the difference increases with perceived severity of the transgression

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